

Cooperate via Open Console

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Abstract

The *Open Console* project builds cooperation in sharing knowledge about websites and domain-names. Three groups of parties are involved: parties who publish facts about those websites and domains (for instance, related geographical locations), parties who interpret those facts (f.i., to improve search results), and the owners of the website and domain-names (f.i. to see what people are publishing about them).

In the context of search engines, Open Console will offer to the website owner features which resemble *Google Search Console*[1]: a place where the owner can communicate with Google. Owners can provide Google with useful information about their website, and get feedback about crawler and visitor activity as reward. This contact gives Google a serious competitive advantage. In contrast to Google's service, the Open Console will provide one interface shared between all competitors in the field.

The sheer size of internet, makes this simple idea into a complex infrastructure. How to handle a few hundred producers, thousands of consumers, and a few hundred million website owners? For application in the OSF context: what does OpenWebSearch want to communicate with the website owners via Open Console?

COLLECTING FACTS

The most visual component of search engines is text processing: indexing text from a huge number of websites, and smart text retrieval algorithms. But those search algorithms can produce better results when they can include additional facts which surround those texts.

To give some examples:

- location information, which is found on a different page in the same website;
- a fresh list of publicly known phishing sites;
- manually confirmed websites which contain rated images to tune child-protection filters; or
- statistics about the popularity and trust-worthiness of the site.

Some information is already available somewhere in internet, but discovery and sharing is not organized.

Not only interpretation facts are useful to share, also crawler activity can be helped:

- website owners publish the frequency of change for certain pages, to optimize being crawled;

- crawlers report technical issues in the visited websites;
- network discovery algorithms flag SEO link-farms, to be excluded from indexing; and so on.

The facts to share about websites, far extend features offered by current generic mechanisms, as there are robots.txt files[2], various types of sitemaps, and various sets of HTML contained meta-data.

The definition of the exchanged "facts" follows the usual standardization processes. It is convenient when consumers have to process better standardized facts, but it is not a requirement for publishers to cooperate. Fact definition is outside the scope of Open Console itself. Open Console is a distribution mechanism.

CHALLENGES

The Open Console project is committed to be open and fair, in their strict interpretation. Fair means: there is not a single party which can monopolize the exchange mechanisms and the relation to the website owners. This calls for strong privacy and defensive strategies.

The amount of data to be exchanged, the independent producers and consumers, and the (potentially) huge amount of interactive users, demand an unmanaged network of independent systems. All logical components must be able to evolve over time, without global synchronized software upgrades.

DESIGN

The implementation of Open Console has some components which are well understood, but also a few parts which have never been done before. Especially the fully *Open* character and the required scale, make even simple components to be challenging to realize.

Easily identifiable main components:

- Consumers and producers agree on a license on distributed facts. The license enforces the

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handling of corrections (take-down requests, removal of errors, expiration);

- The consumers and producers maintain a (semi-)continuous stream of updates, which may reach terabytes in size, containing billions of facts per day;
- A person registers at any "console provider" which offers interactive services. Even this component permits competing implementations. The person proves ownership to one or more websites and domains;
- The owner invites producers of facts to its set-up: selects the sources of interest which are presented in "a fair way". Only invited producers get two-way communication to the owner;
- The two-way communication implements extended dynamic forms with versioning, authorization, and translation features; and
- Producers, consumers, and console providers shape an Association to protect the rules of behavior: the level of openness, the

interpretation of fairness, guaranteed security, and optimal privacy.

The presentation will discuss complications and suggested solutions for these components.

Besides, a start has been made to inventorize the specific facts which participants in the OWS-project wish to exchange with website owners, based on Google's example. The first steps to create the two-way communication between OWS-projects and website owners.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project would not have been possible without the generous initial support of the NLnet Foundation.

REFERENCES

- [1] *Google Search Console*, <https://search.google.com/search-console/about>
- [2] *Robots.txt*, IETF RFC9303, <https://www.rfc-editor.org/info/rfc9309>